

Air and Water Microplastics Detection & Refinement System with Advanced Technology

An Integrated Eco-Friendly Innovation for Urban as well as Rural Pollution Control

Submitted by

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Abstract

At present, environmental pollution is causing critical threats for the living world, animals as well as plants. It is noticeable that most of the pollutions are happening due to some common factors. Air and water containing microplastics and other pollutants have become one of the most critical environmental threats in urban areas as well as rural and remote areas, affecting both human health and ecosystems. This research aims to develop a system that will be capable of detecting microplastics in outdoor air and water sources, particularly in roadside and industrial zones, slums, polluted areas, and ponds, rivers, seas, and other water sources. The system integrates a microplastic detection module utilizing some sensors and filtration, along with a high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filtration unit powered by a renewable energy source like solar energy, utilizing efficient power by solar panels. This system or rover model is designed to be portable like a vehicle, making it suitable for widespread application. This innovation provides a scalable, eco-friendly solution to two major pollution challenges and holds potential for smart city integration and environmental protection initiatives. Besides, the concept and main filtration process of water sources are also knocking on the doors to save the world.

***Keywords:** Microplastics, Air pollution, HEPA filter, Eco-friendly, sensors, scalable etc.*

Introduction

According to the Guardian, every year, over 11 million tons of plastic waste enter our environment. Now, microplastics have been found in human blood, lungs, and even the placenta. Moreover, in recent years, the world has witnessed an alarming rise in environmental pollution. It is being caused by microplastics and airborne particulate matter. Even microplastics—tiny plastic particles less than 5 millimeters in size—have been detected in human blood and lungs. As a result, it has raised serious concerns about the long-term effect on human health. At the same time, air pollution in urban and roadside environments has emerged as a significant contributor to cardiovascular diseases. Microplastics and toxic gases from vehicles and industrial activities are degrading air quality throughout the world. Besides, microplastics are entering our food chain through the water sources.

In spite of those harsh circumstances, implementing the prevention system remains a significant challenge. Microplastic detection techniques are often lab-based, expensive, and inaccessible to the general masses. Similarly, highly efficient air purification and refinement systems are usually designed for indoor use and are rarely adaptable for outdoor environments such as streets, highways, or boats. Now, a pivotal need has arisen for an affordable, portable, and multipurpose device that can detect the pollutants from air as well as water simultaneously and contribute to mitigating the effect.

To bridge the gap, our research introduces a novel, portable, affordable, multipurpose, dual-function (detection & purification), eco-friendly environmental protection system in both air and water. The proposed project is designed to detect the presence of microplastics in water sources. It uses a low-cost optical sensor system integrated with filtering and data analysis

components. At the same time, our outdoor air rover incorporates an outdoor air purification unit based on HEPA (High-Efficiency Particulate Air) filter technology, which uses renewable energy sources like solar panels. This system is also lightweight, energy-efficient, affordable, and suitable for installation.

In our research and project, we have separated the air and water rover to make two types of distinct rovers, one for outdoor air and another for water sources. We did it to get a much more efficient, simple, and affordable system than the hybrid (air and water rover combined) rover. Moreover, our innovations get value using the IoT (Internet of Things) technology and AI-based mechanisms.

This paper presents the design, methodology, and testing process of the integrated microplastic detection and outdoor air as well as water refining system. Our objective is to create an eco-friendly solution that not only improves the way to monitor the environment but also actively contributes to mitigating the pollution. With the increasing urgency of climate change and degradation of the environment, our innovation offers a scalable and practical tool to attain sustainability and healthy life. Through this project, we aim to contribute towards building smarter, greener, and cleaner communities throughout the world.

Materials

As our inventions are in a prototype phase, we have outlined our projects in 1:10 scale. Our projects are developed using the following components, categorized into three modules:

a) Microplastic Detection Module:

- i. Nodemcu-ESP8266 : for sensor data processing.
- ii. Dust Sensor : to detect microplastics
- iii. Infrared LED lights : to use in dust sensor
- iv. Turbidity Sensor : to detect water ppm and pollution rate
- v. Power supply : Battery and Solar panel

b) Refining System:

Air Refining System:

- i. HEPA filter (H13 grade or higher) : to trap micro-particles
- ii. Fan : to circulate and absorb outdoor air
- iii. Carbon filter : to isolate micro-plastics

Water Refining System:

- i. Turbine : to circulate the water
- ii. Water Filtration Unit : it is made out of Mesh and activated Carbon filter

c) Body and portability Unit:

- i. Wheels : to make portable
- ii. Motors : to use the motors
- iii. Nodemcu-ESP8266 : to control the rover throughout IoT technology
- iv. Structure : the structure are made for suitability
- v. PVC sheets : to make the cases and parts
- vi. Turbines : to run the rover which is used for water refinement

d) Power Supply:

- i. Battery : we used the Li-ion 7.4V and 2.4V batteries
- ii. Solar panels : to use the renewable and eco energy

Methodology

A. Microplastic Detection

1. Sample Collection

At first, air rover passes by the roads, streets, industrial areas etc. whereas, the water rover works in the water sources like lakes, ponds, rivers, canals, oceans etc. In this protocol, the rovers collect respectively airborne and water samples to suspect the microplastics and other pollutants.

2. Detection Mechanism

Some Infrared LED lights were directed through the airborne and water sample. The Dust sensor measured variations in intensity, scattering patterns and turbidity sensor is to estimate the concentration of microplastics.

3. Data Analysis

Sensors readings were calibrated using standard air and water samples with known microplastic content to estimate particle per million (ppm) and Nephelometric Turbidity Unit (NTU). The readings were processed by some complex equations and it is stored in the online database by IoT technology.

B. Refining Mechanism

1. Filtration Setup:

Polluted air was drawn into the system via a fan and passed through a HEPA filter which is housed inside a casing. Turbines were used to do that task in the water rover.

2. Filtration Process

Then, the samples were passed through a fine mesh and activated carbon filter to isolate solid particles specially, microplastics. After that, these particles and pollutants were stored in a storage.

3. Performance Monitoring

Another sensor measures the air and water quality after filtration. The difference between input and output levels are quantified. All the system are monitored by IoT technology and fully automated.

4. Pollution free output

After the process, pollutant free air and water are passed through another way.

C. Portability

The rovers are controlled by Nodemcu-ESP8266. Hence, we can use the IoT technology. They were scalable, automated and efficient.

D. Power Supply

Our rovers are designed to be used by the solar panels and batteries. In this prototype, we used not only the batteries but also solar panels. It is eco-friendly, renewable and affordable system.

Materials and Methods

Figure-1:materials and process

Results

The initial prototype of the microplastics detector was able to identify particulate matter in controlled water and air samples under both lab and outdoor condition.

Using the dust sensor and the infrared LED lights, light scattering was observed. By that, we determined the microplastics levels and the amount of the pollutants. Turbidity sensor was used for more accurate reading.

For the air refining system, fans absorbed the polluted air. Polluted air entered to the HEPA filtration unit. By the mesh and activated carbon filter, microplastics and other pollutants are isolated and then refined air was released.

For the water refining system, turbines helped to intake the water filtration unit. Then, water was refined through the water filtration unit.

It is noticeable that, the microplastics level and rate of pollutants were much more than the outdoor environment in both theoretically and practically. Even, more microplastics and polluted particles were absorbed in the outdoor condition.

Although precise measurement of particle size and composition was not conducted at this stage, the early results support further development and testing. So, future development is needed to get more efficient results.

Figure-1: PPM in Lab and Polluted Air (Avg. PM 2.5 & PM 10)

Figure-2: Turbidity Sensor read in Stored and Polluted Water (Avg.)

Discussion

The goal of our project was to make a prototype or a system which will be able to detect microplastics in water and outdoor air simultaneously. The results from initial lab tests revealed noticeable differences in pollutant concentration, particularly in the standards of PPM and turbidity values NTU between clean and contaminated samples.

The air purification module, built with a HEPA-based filter and active carbon support, showed moderate efficiency in isolating microplastics and pollutants in lab environment. However, the outdoor air performance needs further enhancement and upgradation.

Similarly, it is noticeable that the system can potentially detect physical water contamination through basic optical and filtration-based methods.

Nevertheless, since our project is still in its early prototype phase, some limitations were observed:

- Sensor precision was not fully optimal, leading to slight inconsistencies in multiple measurements.
- Humidity and ambient particles, sometimes impacted data accuracy
- The material used for making the body (e.g. PVC boards) may not be sustainable for long run.
- Field deployment remains slightly theoretical and needs further upgradation.

Future development will focus on enhancing the sensitivity, improving the digital monitoring systems and interfaces, and implementing large-scale field trials. Additional improvements will aim to improve portability, energy efficiency and mechanism based on new generation based technology.

Conclusion

The current prototypes of our Microplastic Detection and air as well as water refinement system serves as an early-stage of a novel, scalable, effective, durable, portable and eco-friendly environment savior technology.

While full-scale testing and optimization are yet to be completed, the initial build confirms the technical possibility of our design.

Our next steps include enhancing detection accuracy, improving filtration performance in outdoor settings, and implementing smart features as soon as possible.

This project has strong potential to contribute to pollution monitoring and control, particularly in all countries and regions around the world to mitigate the severe climate change and raise a weapon against severe environmental challenges.

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Appendices

Materials and Methods

Figure-5: Air Rover (ECO- Zephyr X)

Figure-6: Water Rover (ECO – Hydra X)

Figure 6 &7 : Estimated Real life structure of outdoor air and water rovers